

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article gives information about the conditions for the formation of creative competence of future primary school teachers and the ways of developing the creativity of pedagogues.*

Keywords: *competence, primary school teachers, creative competence, competence, creativity.*

In recent years, interest in creative thinking, assessment and formation of professional creativity has increased in the field of psychology. The relevance of this problem is determined by modern changes. In the conditions that have arisen, the requirements for such qualities as openness to new experiences, the ability to find solutions in non-standard situations, and a creative attitude to reality have increased. In this regard, new and very important tasks are set before education. One of them is upbringing and education, which helps the full development of a person, his creative aspirations, adaptation of a person to different environments, dynamically changing socio-economic situation. To achieve this goal, the pedagogue himself must have the above-mentioned characteristics of a creative person. In this regard, the question of forming the creative competence of the pedagogue is raised.

Creativity in the competence structure of future elementary school teachers reflects the creative achievements of the pedagogue at various stages of professional activity and is understood as the ability to create new professional products and high results of activity at the expense of the implementation of the individual's creative abilities. , usefulness, and the productivity of pedagogical activity in general, which is expressed in the optimal organization of activities, taking into account the minimization of energy costs, are creative characteristics of the pedagogical activity of a higher education teacher, a school teacher, a kindergarten teacher. In this regard, the existing system of training future elementary school teachers (mainly focused on special knowledge, solution algorithms, proven technologies) and the readiness of the pedagogue to think creatively, make decisions in situations of high uncertainty, uncertainty and responsibility, that is, it is observed that there is a fundamental conflict between the need to develop educational-management methods that provide all the main elements of competence in relation to one's own professional creativity.

All of these aspects required by modern pedagogical activity determine the relevance of conducting research dedicated to the development of professionalism and creativity of competent teachers, the development of various models of the creative improvement of teachers' work. organization of the research of creative competence of primary school teachers and its formation is not just an idle talk, because today there are more than twenty approaches and methodological views, points of view. The choice of one or another approach can be made based on reasons inherent in the educational process. However, this, in turn, is the death of the educational paradigm, which can be directly related to changes in the economic system, social, political and other global changes. change can also be the main, primary reason.

We are studying the issue related to the formation of creative competence (not abilities or personal characteristics, but competence). Thus, this term is a general opinion, a generalized view of our point of view about the advantages of the competence approach to the analysis of this phenomenon. According to scientist A.A. Verbitsky (A.A. Verbitsky, 2010), the educational paradigm has gone through several stages. So, before the institutional period, this paradigm reflected the values of a closed group of people, transmitted as a result of being an example, imitation, coercion. In ancient times, this paradigm elevated the civic values reflected in the dominance of physical and military readiness, education in literacy, active and responsible citizen education. In the Middle Ages, there was a paradigm of Christian education, and this process was completely regulated and controlled by the church. The classical educational paradigm emerged as a response to the growth of industrial production in the 17th century. The main goal of such education is to provide students with the system of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the profession. At present, the formation of a new educational paradigm is taking place. In addition to the research of the above-mentioned author, V.A. Boltov [33], I.A. Zimnyaya [30] and other scientists evidenced by the works. This formation process is quite complicated. It is characterized by the fact that the previous paradigm based on the BMC system can no longer meet the demands of modern education.

All this leads to the need for constant, active and often independent learning, for which it is known that most graduates are not ready. A person who quickly adapts to a team, can work in a team, make decisions, make choices, take initiative, use limited resources effectively, etc. there is a need for a specialist capable of It is self-evident that the productivity of professional activity in this case does not depend on the acquisition of special information that has been given for a lifetime, but on the ability to find one's way in information flows, the ability to take initiative, to solve problems depends on the ability to find and apply missing knowledge or other resources to achieve a given goal. It is self-evident that the education system as a whole and each specific educational institution, each pedagogue cannot fail to react to these changes.

A person-centered approach seems more humane because it assumes and plans for the success of any listener, regardless of their abilities. For this, it is necessary to create conditions that take into account the individual characteristics of the listener. As a result, the pedagogue's attitude, position, point of view is the third difference in the considered approaches. In the implementation of the competence approach, the pedagogue knows exactly what skills the child will develop; he follows the student regardless of his intentions and desires. In contrast to the above-mentioned point of view, person-centered teaching allows for a more humane perspective for the pedagogue, who does not impose his ideas, but works based on the interests of the child, and with him the subject- builds subject relations. Supporters of this approach try to soften the attitude, strictness, and rigidity of the attitude of the pedagogue implementing the competence approach by emphasizing that the pedagogue needs to explain the necessity of this or that skill, its role in the future life, to motivate and interest him.

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